

NH₄⁺, Mg²⁺ AND Ba²⁺ ACTIVITIES IN COLLOIDAL CLAYS IN RELATION TO THE CONCENTRATION OF THE DISPERSED PHASE

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The variation of the activity of NH₄⁺, Mg²⁺ and Ba²⁺ ions in clays with the concentration of the latter has been studied with the help of membrane electrodes. NH₄⁺ -ion activity increases almost linearly up to about 10% clay concentration, after which the rate slows down. This slowing down tendency is more markedly exhibited by the bivalent clays, particularly Mg-clay, even at a comparatively low concentration.

The percentage dissociation of NH₄⁺, Mg- and Ba-clays shows an initial rise to a maximum at 1.1%, 1.4% and 0.7%, respectively, of the clays. The subsequent fall is sharp, but after about 5-6% clay concentration the curves are nearly flat. NH₄-clay, however, behaves differently and shows a second maximum followed by a gradual fall up to the highest (14%) clay concentration studied.

Clay-membrane electrodes for the determination of cationic activities were developed by Marshall ("Colloid Chemistry of the Silicate Minerals", Academic Press, 1949). Later on Marshall *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) and Marshall and Chatterjee (*J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1950, 54, 671) used the membrane electrodes to study the variation of metal-ion activities in the course of neutralisation of acid colloidal clays with hydroxides and oxides of Na, K, NH₄, Ca, Mg and Ba. Mitra (D. Phil. thesis, Calcutta University, 1954) using a number of Indian clays prepared clay-membrane electrodes, suitable for measurements of ionic activities over a wide range, and reported measurements of Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Zn²⁺, and Cu²⁺ ion activities with the help of membrane electrodes.

Cationic activity measurements are generally made with dilute suspensions, and the results are often used directly to elucidate ion-exchange characteristics of clays present in soil. However, the clay, as it occurs in the soil, is more or less gel-like and it hardly assumes a sol state under natural conditions. Hence there may be little justification for extrapolating information available in dilute solutions to concentrated pastes. With this end in view, the author determined the variation of Na⁺, K⁺, and Ca²⁺ ion activity in colloidal clays over a wide range of concentrations of the disperse phase (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 399). The present enquiry is a continuation of the same work with other ions, viz., NH₄⁺, Mg²⁺ and Ba²⁺.

EXPERIMENTAL

The clay-membrane electrodes were prepared as reported earlier by Chatterjee (*loc. cit.*). The clay membranes fixed to one end of a pyrex tubing separated the base-saturated clay suspension or paste from a solution of known ionic activity (of say, NH₄Cl, MgCl₂ or BaCl₂ solution). The potential difference across the membrane between two tiny calomel electrodes was measured with the help of a Cambridge potentiometer. The ionic activity was calculated from E.M.F. of the cell:

Hg/Hg₂Cl₂/NH₄(Mg or Ba) chloride/Membrane/NH₄(Mg or Ba) clay/Hg₂Cl₂/Hg,
using the Nernst equation,

$$E = \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a(\text{solution})}{a(\text{clay})} .$$

The variation of cationic activity with concentration of the clay was studied exactly in a manner reported earlier (Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*).

The results of a_{NH_4} , a_{Mg} and a_{Ba} determinations are shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2, and recorded in Tables I-III.

TABLE I

Variation of NH_4 -ion activity with conc. of clay suspension.

Clay suspen- sion (g./100g.).	Total molal NH_4^+ conc. in clay (c).	NH_4^+ ion ac- tivity of clay (a).	% Dissocia- tion. ($a/c \times 100$).	Clay suspen- sion (g./100g.).	Total molal NH_4^+ conc. in clay (c).	NH_4^+ ion ac- tivity of clay (a).	% Dissocia- tion ($a/c \times 100$).
14.1	0.117	703×10^{-8}	6.0	4.7	0.039	254.9×10^{-8}	6.5
11.5	0.096	650.1	6.8	3.8	0.032	191.20	6.05
10.2	0.085	613	7.2	3.2	0.027	162.80	6.1
9.3	0.077	579	7.5	1.9	0.016	98.24	6.2
7.5	0.062	448	7.2	1.1	0.0091	59.07	6.5
6.3	0.052	355.9	6.8	0.74	0.0061	37.53	6.1
5.4	0.045	289.4	6.4	0.56	0.0046	27.82	6.0

TABLE II

Variation of Mg-ion activity with the conc. of clay suspension.

Known Mg^{2+} ion activity = 0.0001.

Clay suspension (g./100g.).	Total molal Mg^{2+} conc. in clay (c).	Mg^{2+} activity of clay ($a \times 10^6$).	% Dissociation ($a/c \times 100$).
11.70	0.048	1.86	0.0039
7.96	0.033	1.31	0.0040
6.04	0.025	1.17	0.0046
4.70	0.019	1.09	0.0056
2.46	0.010	0.85	0.0083
1.38	0.005	0.63	0.0120
0.78	0.003	0.31	0.0098
0.43	0.002	0.17	0.0087

TABLE III

Variation of Ba-ion activity with the conc. of clay suspension.

Known Ba^{2+} ion activity = 0.0001.

Clay suspension (g./100g.).	Total molal Ba^{2+} conc. in clay (c).	Ba^{2+} activity of clay ($a \times 10^6$).	% Dissociation ($a/c \times 100$).
8.40	0.037	2.09	0.0056
6.80	0.030	1.82	0.0060
5.70	0.025	1.55	0.0061
4.90	0.021	1.32	0.0061
4.30	0.019	1.02	0.0054
2.90	0.013	0.89	0.0069
1.80	0.008	0.61	0.0077
0.68	0.003	0.31	0.0105
0.52	0.002	0.16	0.0070

DISCUSSION

The nature of the variation of the activity of NH_4^+ ion is more or less similar to that of the monovalent Na^+ and K^+ ions (Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*). Variations in the case of Mg^{2+} and Ba^{2+} are similar to those of the bivalent Ca^{2+} ions (*loc. cit.*). There is, however, some difference between the behaviour of NH_4^+ clays and the Na^+ and K^+ clays. Firstly, the initial slope of the NH_4^+ ion activity curve is less than that of either Na^+ or K^+ ion activity curve and, secondly, after an

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

almost linear run, the NH_4^+ ion activity curve flattens at about 10% clay concentration. Similar curves obtained with the electrolytes in aqueous solution do not show any flattening tendency. In fact, the variation of mean ionic activity of electrolytes in aqueous solution is nearly linear up to or even beyond the molal concentration of the ion as it obtains in the clay salts. The behaviour of base-saturated clay suspensions at higher concentrations is most probably due to the overlapping of the double layers, which causes a decrease in the number of ions registering their activities.

The curves for Mg^{2+} and Ba^{2+} ions also flatten out like that of NH_4^+ ion but at much lower concentrations of the clays.

Tables I, II and III record in the last column the percentage dissociation of the respective ion, calculated from the observed activity (a) and the total concentration (c) of the ion present in the base-saturated clay. The percentage dissociation of Ba^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions shows an initial increase with concentration followed by a fall after a maximum, but at high concentrations the rate of decrease markedly slows down. NH_4^+ clay, on the other hand, shows two maxima, one near about 1% concentration, similar to the bivalent clays, and the other at about 9% concentration. The second maximum is higher than the first. It is, however, to be noted that the NH_4 -clay is nearly one hundred times more dissociated than the bivalent clays, and in this respect it is similar to the Na- and K-clays. The latter unlike NH_4 -, Mg- and Ba-clays show an initial minimum followed by a maximum.

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